

Drone data collection protocol using DJI Mavic 3E/3M RTK

Seabird mapping with SeaBee

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Scope

This protocol provides standardized guidelines for seabird mapping using DJI Mavic 3E/3T/3M RTK series drones as part of the SeaBee project. The primary objective is to collect high-resolution aerial imagery to document nesting seabird colonies efficiently and with minimal disturbance to sensitive species.

Drone-based surveys offer a more accurate and less disruptive alternative to traditional colony walk-throughs for surface-nesting seabirds. Additionally, the imagery serves as a permanent record, allowing for future reanalysis and long-term monitoring. By following this protocol, field teams will contribute to a valuable dataset that improves our understanding of seabird populations and habitat use, supporting conservation and monitoring efforts.

The protocol emphasizes a balance between data quality and ecological responsibility. It includes guidance on pre-flight planning, mission setup, data gathering, and post-flight procedures to streamline data collection across diverse and sometimes challenging environments. The protocol also integrates manual observations and GPS logging to ensure that most of the accessible islands and nesting spots are mapped and provide a comprehensive view of seabird distributions.

Detailed instructions are also provided for the safe handling and operation of drones, including wind and terrain considerations, restricted areas, and preflight and in-flight safety checks. Specific guidance on altitude and speed settings for different seabird species helps minimize disturbance and improve data quality.

Data collected follows an established workflow, including storage, processing, and annotation, to ensure data integrity and consistency. Images are uploaded to a centralized platform, where automated scripts create georeferenced mosaics that can be accessed by researchers and integrated into a machine learning framework for species detection. With this protocol, field teams play an integral role in expanding the database for seabird monitoring, with each dataset contributing to species-specific models and validation efforts. This structured approach aims to foster a sustainable and scalable methodology for seabird conservation efforts across Norway's coastal ecosystems.

This protocol is part of research funded by the Research Council of Norway, grant ID #296478, to the Norwegian Infrastructure for drone-based research, mapping, and monitoring in the coastal zone (SeaBee). The Norwegian Institute for Water Research (NIVA) is acknowledged for handling and sharing of drone data.

Workflow in field

Each field team is assigned a designated area to map. The setup may vary between teams depending on the terrain and water conditions they need to navigate. In protected waters, teams will typically use smaller open boats, while teams heading to more exposed islands or coastal stretches will operate from larger, chartered vessels. The project leader will provide details on the specific setup for each team before data collection begins.

What to map

The primary objective is to map all surface nesting seabirds within the designated areas. Ideally, all islands or potential nesting spots should be visited (Figure 1). The most efficient method is to sail by islands and use binoculars to spot seabirds on land. For larger islands, complete circumnavigation may be necessary.

Figure 1. Example of GPS tracks (black line) from one survey day. At the red dots seabird colonies were mapped using a drone while green dots are birds manually entered in the urpop database.

For this work we consider a bird as nesting if it is actively sitting on a nest. Birds that appear in pairs but do not have a nest (e.i. failed breeding) are counted as territorial.

- The project leader will provide a QGIS project with historical nesting observations, and these spots should be prioritized. Import the project into QField on a mobile phone or tablet for easy navigation in field.
- Always keep the provided GPS tracker on to record a log of which areas have been checked.

How to collect the data

The drone mapping is generally deployed for the species great black-backed gull (*Larus marinus*), herring gull (*Larus argentatus*), lesser black-backed gull (*Larus fuscus*), common gull (*Larus canus*), black-headed gull (*Chroicocephalus ridibundus*), arctic tern (*Sterna paradisaea*), common tern (*Sterna hirundo*), and great cormorant (*Phalacrocorax carbo*).

Whenever possible, colonies of the above-mentioned species should be flown with drones, as it provides better data quality and documentation. However, there are situations where using the drone is not necessary, including:

- Very small islands/areas.
- Islands/areas where it is easy to get a clear overview with few nesting birds (<5 nests).
- Islands/areas that contain only non-nesting birds.

In these cases and for other species of nesting seabirds, observations are manually logged in QField.

- Enter editing mode (Figure 2). The only layer you can edit is the 'mapping data' so it automatically selects this layer.

Figure 2. QField interface with all available layers. The editing mode is entered by pressing the pencil in the bottom right corner of the layer menu.

- Navigate the cursor to the location of the bird and press the plus button in the bottom right corner.
- **Species:** select correct species
- **Count:** number of units counted
- **Unit:** What you counted. We prefer to count occupied nests if possible. Birds that are not on nests but appear to have a territory should be marked as “apparently occupied territory”.
- When done, press the tick mark in the top left corner of the menu (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Species observation menu in QField.

Given that the project covers both early and late-nesting species, and only one survey is conducted, make sure to log species that are not actively on nests, such as oystercatchers and terns, in the app for areas that are also flown with the drone.

For islands that have been surveyed but **have no birds or nests**, mark them as empty in the bird logger site using "Annet" for species and "Ikke funnet" for activity.

Pre-flight planning and programming

Colonies are usually flown in pre-programmed missions using grid patterns (e.g. “lawnmower” style) while taking timed photos every two seconds. This approach ensures: 1) sequential and systematic image capture; 2) sufficient forward and sideways overlap between photos; and 3) comprehensive coverage of the area. These factors ease the stitching process and improve the overall quality of the resulting orthomosaic, providing a more detailed and accurate composite image of the surveyed colony.

Setting up a mission

1. Manually create a new mission on DJI Pilot 2 app in the remote controller
2. Draw a polygon around the area you want to map. Include a buffer zone around the area and avoid including people, buildings, roads and other structures. If an island does not contain people, structures like lighthouses or boat houses can be included in the imagery.
3. Select correct drone and camera
4. Rename the mission to island or area name
5. **Ortho Collection:** leave as default
6. **Ortho GSD:** leave as default
7. **Altitude mode:** in most cases select Relative to Takeoff Point (ALT). With this setting the elevation is calculated from the takeoff point.
8. **Route altitude:** set according to species and terrain (see `Mission altitude and flight speed` and `Wind considerations and restrictions` below).
9. **Elevation optimization:** disabled
10. **Safe Takeoff Altitude:** after takeoff the drone ascends to this height and flies to the mission start point.
11. **Speed:** set according to bird species and conditions
12. Change the **course angle** to reduce mission time.
13. **Upon completion:** set to `Exit task` (hovers). If set to `return to home` the drone will return to the take-off point and likely land in the sea and if it is set to `land` the drone will land at the last waypoint in the mission.

Under Advanced Settings, ensure the following have been set:

1. **Side Overlap Ratio (%):** 70-80%. Overlap between the flight lines.
2. **Frontal Overlap Ratio (%):** 70-80%. Overlap along the flight line. The side and forward overlap ratios are important in the image processing where image matching

is performed to align images based on matching points. Adequate overlap ratios ensure good image matching in the final orthomosaic data product.

3. **Take off speed:** This is the speed from the takeoff point to the first waypoint in the mission. Set this to match the mission flight speed or lower. You can always speed up the approach manually if needed.
4. **Photo mode:** default 'Timed interval shot'.

Camera settings:

- Make sure the camera exposure is good. Sometimes the Auto mode setting is fine. However, when flying over cormorant colonies, exposed rock, or in conditions with a lot of sun or heavy cloud cover, manual adjustments may be necessary to avoid overexposure or underexposure. This can be done manually preflight or when the drone is in the air.

Mission altitude and flight speed

The altitude and speed for flight missions depends on the bird species, the colony's response, and the general conditions at the time of the flight. There is no direct speed limit, but it is better to start cautiously and adjust later to avoid disturbing the birds. In general, smaller species require slower flight speeds, with terns needing a particularly slow speed - often no more than 1 m/s.

Make sure that the take-off speed matches or is slower than the mission speed. The standard settings for different bird species are listed below:

Cormorants and large gulls (herring and great black-backed gulls):

- Altitude: 40 m.a.s.l.
- Speed: 5-7 m/s

Smaller gulls (common gull, lesser black-backed gull):

- Altitude: 30 m.a.s.l.
- Speed: 3-5 m/s

Terns and black headed gull:

- Altitude: 15-20 m.a.s.l.
- Speed: 1-5 m/s

If necessary, the altitude for large gulls can be increased to a maximum of 60 meters above ground to speed up the mission, but this should be the exception rather than the rule.

Wind considerations and restrictions

High wind speeds can significantly reduce a drone's flight time, sometimes by more than half, and you can experience large fluctuations in estimated remaining flight time depending on whether the drone is flying with or against the wind. To avoid running out of battery mid-flight, always make sure the drone has enough power to get back to the landing point safely. In high winds, take off and fly against the wind to the colony so that the return trip with a tailwind uses less battery.

Keep in mind that wind speed typically increases with altitude. The drone's windspeed readings are shown on the controller. Consider flying slower to avoid motion blur in high winds.

DJI's Mavic 3 is rated for a maximum wind resistance of 12 m/s and a top wind speed of 21 m/s.

Terrain considerations

The flight altitude is by default relative to the take-off point (ALT), and in most cases, missions can be flown relative to the take-off point even when the terrain fluctuates.

Very high terrain

In situations where entire islands or areas are consistently and significantly higher than the take-off location, you can adjust the flight altitude to correct for the height difference. Just keep in mind that this adjustment will result in flying at a higher altitude over lower terrain areas of the colony, which could impact the detail of the data collected in those regions.

Terrain higher than mission altitude

When colonies are located on areas with steep inclines, where parts of the terrain come close to or exceeds the preferred flight altitude, increasing the altitude for the whole area results in poor image quality for lower sections. Instead change the altitude mode to follow the terrain:

1. Altitude Mode: Set to AGL (Above Ground Level)
2. Enable "Real-Time Follow"

3. Set altitude under “Terrain Follow Altitude”
4. Take off and put on obstacle avoidance
5. Turn it back off before landing

Restricted areas and no-fly zones

Some airspace is either permanently or temporarily restricted for drone flying. For example, it is prohibited to fly over or near protected areas and national parks, military zones, city centers, gas terminals, prisons and embassies, and oil platforms. All drone pilots are required to check the areas in which they are going to fly.

Permanent restricted areas are set by the CCA Norway and are found either in list format or on the Norwegian Aeronautical map (links are below). On the map, areas marked in a solid red line always have an active restriction in place while areas marked in a dashed red line have active restriction when listed in NOTAM (notice to airmen). Also note that restriction areas start with "EN R" while "EN D" denotes a danger area. Temporary restrictions on airspace are not included in the Aeronautical map or list. These and some permanently restricted areas such as airports are shown in NOTAM.

Resources for Checking Restricted Airspace:

- Permanently restricted airspace in list format: [AIP Norge - Avinor](#)
- Norwegian Aeronautical Map: [Norway Aeronautical chart ICAO 500.000 \(arcgis.com\)](#)
- NOTAM: [IPPC - Norwegian Aerodrome Info](#)

Airports

All airports in Norway have a 5 km restriction radius around runways. Flying within this radius requires explicit permission from the control tower. Each airport may have different procedures for obtaining this approval, so it's important to check the specifics for each location.

- Some airports require you to **call the tower** immediately before the flight to request permission.
- Others require drone pilots to **register their flight on NINOX**, after which they must wait for approval.

National parks and protected areas

All nature reserves eligible for seabird mapping with drones have been applied for through Statsforvalteren (the Norwegian Environmental Agency) before the start of the field season.

Preflight checks

Before starting a mission or launching the drone, carry out the following checks.

Drone inspection:

1. Carefully inspect the drone and its propellers, checking for any cracks, warping, or damage that could affect flight performance.

On the drone controller:

1. Confirm that the memory card has sufficient storage space for the mission
2. **RTK** should be enabled
3. Disable **Obstacle Avoidance**. If this is enabled, the drone will either break before or avoid obstacles which can prevent you from performing hand landings.
4. Set '**Signal Lost Action**' to Hover.

Weather and surroundings:

1. Assess the weather conditions. If it has started raining, do not proceed with the flight.
2. Evaluate the surroundings -check for any people, or obstacles that may have entered the area.

Take-off and landing:

Manual take-off and landing from the hand, especially when operating from boats, are recommended (Figure 4). Preferably outside of the area to be mapped.

1. Ensure that the drone is securely held and clear of obstructions before initiating take-off.
2. Use the remote control to start the motors and takeoff manually. When ready start the mission (press the 'Play' button on the mission).

Figure 4. Examples of takeoff from the hand on smaller boats. In both cases the remote controller is supported on the legs as it requires input on both joystick to start the drone propellers.

Keep the boat at a good distance from the island. Usually there is no need to be closer than 200 meters. If one needs to be closer, keep a close eye on the colony as birds may leave their nests due to the proximity.

Data gathering

For any flight, follow the rules set by CCA Norway and operate within the scope of your drone license (see Appendix 2). Always avoid flying over people, boats, major roads, or buildings if possible.

Approach with the drone

Closely monitor the birds for any response to the drone while approaching the island. If the colony flushes (i.e. most birds take flight) or if birds are moving of their nests, try the one of the following approaches:

- Pause the mission and let the drone hover until the birds have settled.
- Proceed with the approach, pause the mission at the start point and let the drone hover until the birds have settled.
- Manually approach at a lower speed using the joystick after the mission is resumed.

Some species are more sensitive to the drone:

- **Oystercatchers** often react to the drone by issuing vocal warning calls or pursuing the drone in flight. They are unlikely to stop this behavior until well into the mission or after the drone has landed. Unless they disturb the other birds or repeatedly come very close to the drone, proceed with the flight.
- **Terns** have a tendency to flush easily when the drone is flying, especially early in the nesting season. In some rare cases they may dive at the drone, attempting to attack it. Terns are more likely to habituate to the drone, so before aborting the flight, one can try to hover further away from the colony until they have returned to their nests.

During the flight

1. Continue to closely monitor the birds for any response to the drone. If the birds are reacting to the drone, try the measures listed under “Approach”. If there are **serious negative responses** from the birds, the mission should be canceled, and the drone flown up (in altitude) and back towards the pilot/away from the colony.
2. Closely monitor the drone’s flight and data collection during the mission. If pictures seem over- or underexposed pause the mission and adjust camera settings. This can either be done by changing the ISO or aperture.
3. Monitor the surrounding area for any obstacles and changes in weather.
 - If the area contains smaller roads or footpaths keep an eye on possible traffic. If traffic occurs, pause the mission until traffic passes.

Battery or SD card replacement

Replacing either the battery or SD card during a mission will result in two separate folders being created for storing photos. Both folders will have the same mission name and should be combined during post-processing.

1. Pause the mission.
2. Fly the drone back and land.
3. Power down the drone, if changing battery.

4. Replace the battery or SD card.
5. Launch the drone again.
6. On the controller, choose resume mission.

Cancelled missions

If a mission is canceled before the entire colony has been mapped, please keep track of that. Name the folder with a suffix of "FAILED," "CANCELLED," or "HALF" on the SD card before uploading the data and send the a description of cancelled flight to project leader.

Potential issues and troubleshooting

During drone operations, several issues can arise. Below are some common problems and how to handle them:

- **Drone Automatically Returning to Home (RTH):**
If the drone initiates "Return to Home", cancel the automatic return either by using the touch screen or by pressing pause button on the controller and fly it back manually
- **Connection loss between drone and remote controller:**
Pay attention to the signal strength between the drone and the remote controller. If the drone loses connection to the controller, it should hover in place, assuming the settings were programmed correctly. Move to a better location to reestablish connection with the drone. This typically happens when terrain or other obstacles are between the drone and the controller.
- **Loss of live image feed:**
At times, the drone may lose image transfer to the remote controller, causing the camera view on the screen to freeze. Even though the live feed is interrupted, the drone continues to store photos on the SD card, and this can be verified through the information on the controller screen. Keep flying the mission based on the pre-programmed flight path if you are confident in the drone's position and behavior.
- **Unusual drone behavior:**
If the drone starts flying erratically, exhibits unstable flight patterns, or doesn't respond as expected, immediately return it to the take-off point and land safely. Check for any issues with the calibration, wind conditions, or potential obstructions before relaunching.

Post-flight

Pack down the drone between every flight to protect it, especially when in an open boat or at high sea.

1. Power down drone and remote controller
2. Remove drone battery and place in charging station (if necessary)
3. Place remote controller in charging station (if necessary)
4. Replace gimbal cover
5. Fold the drone and remote controller and place in case
6. Store the case in a waterproof bag if on open boat

End of day: Charge all equipment (drone batteries, remote controller, power bank, internet link, GPS, etc.). Leave the drone case open and take out the drone overnight to get rid of moisture.

Data upload

The data upload described here is specific to the use of the SeaBee infrastructure.

Data structure

Data is uploaded to MinIO based on the general project documentation ([SeaBee Documentation - Data upload](#)). For seabird missions, mission folders names should follow the “grouping_area_yyyymmddHHMM” structure, for instance “moere-og-romsdal-heroy_kvernavagen_202405311140”. Please avoid using æøå in the folder names itself. This folder name itself is however not used for the automated processes. These folders are then placed in the `seabirds/yyyy/` folder on MinIO.

The automated processes all gather information from the `config.seabee.yaml`, that have to be included in the folder. The `other` folder is optional, and from a data upload standpoint used to store images that should not be included in the mosaicking in the subfolder `unused`.

The file `config.seabee.yaml` has a fixed structure that need to be followed:

```
grouping: Møre-og-Romsdal-Herøy      # General identifier linking this flight to related flights
area: Kvernavågen                    # Name of specific location
datetime: '202405311140'             # 'yyyymmddHHMM' or 'yyyymmdd'. Quotes are required
nfiles: 290                           # Total number of files in the 'images' folder
organisation: NINA                    # Responsible organisation
mosaic: true                           # Whether to mosaic the raw images using ODM (true or false)
classify: true                         # Whether to classify the orthomosaic using machine learning
publish: true                           # Whether to publish the orthophoto to GeoNode
theme: Seabirds                       # SeaBee "theme" ('Seabirds', 'Mammals' or 'Habitat')
creator_name: Sindre Molvørsmyr      # [Optional]. Data collector/pilot
project: Seabirds2023                 # [Optional]. Name of project
```

Non-mission folders, that are not supposed to be processed through the pipeline are uploaded as they are in the subfolder `yyyy/nonmission/`.

After the images are organized into the intended structure and config files created, the data can be uploaded to MinIO. We recommend using Rclone to copy the data for stability. The process to install and setup Rclone is described in [SeaBee Documentation - Storage](#).

If you have a computer where you cannot setup Environment Variables yourself (like a NINAPC), you can set up an alias using DOSKEY

```
rclone="C:/Users/sindre.molvarsmyr/OneDrive - NINA/Portable
tech/rclone-v1.60.1-windows-amd64/rclone.exe" %*. This again can be set
up using a .bat file and a windows shortcut with target = %windir%\system32\cmd.exe
/k "C:\Users\sindre.molvarsmyr\OneDrive - NINA\Portable
```

tech\rclone-v1.60.1-windows-amd64\doskey.bat", where the doskey.bat is a text file with the doskey command.

Data upload procedure from field season 2024

At the end of every field day, all data collected should be copied to the provided hard drive and uploaded to the project cloud (minio/sigma/SeaBee). If any changes need to be made to mission folders, do it before starting the upload to the cloud. This may include:

- Deleting pictures that include people (IMPORTANT!).
- Merging folders where one flight got split over multiple folders.
- Renaming cancelled missions.

Edit the data either on the SD card using a laptop or on the hard drive after the data is copied to it. If you are editing on the hard drive, remember to update the **nfiles** parameter in the config file (created when copying to hard drive, see steps below).

Steps for uploading the data:

1. Power on the Raspberry Pi and internet link. The raspberry should automatically connect to the Wi-Fi hotspot
2. Plug in the SD card and hard drive to the Raspberry Pi.
3. Upload the data using one of three options displayed on the screen
 - **Copy to hard drive:** Copies only the files from the SD card to the hard drive. It will also create a config file needed when uploading to the cloud, that includes the number of files in the folder.
 - **Upload to cloud:** Uploads the data from the hard drive to the project cloud.
 - **Do both:** Copies the files from the SD card to the hard drive and then uploads the data to the project cloud.
4. When the data upload is complete, press the eject button in the screen and remove the hard drive and SD card

Depending on the strength and speed of the internet connection, the upload may take many hours. If the data transfer is interrupted, the Raspberry Pi will track which files have already been uploaded or copied. Simply restart the transfer by following the steps above.

The folder structure of the SD card and hard drive will be the following:

SD Card	Hard Drive
---------	------------

DCIM DJI_YYYYMMDDHHMM_NNN [images go here] DJI_YYYYMMDDHHMM_NNN_missionname [images go here]	DJI_YYYYMMDDHHMM_NNN [images go here] config.seabee.yaml DJI_YYYYMMDDHHMM_NNN_missionname [images go here] config.seabee.yaml
--	--

Data upload procedure for 2025

There will be a new upload procedure in 2025 as we identified multiple problems with the procedure from 2024. A Windows application is in the works and will replace the Raspberry Pi powered device used in 2024. The hope is that a system on a Windows laptop will feel more familiar to many and that in case of bugs and errors users will be able to fix them themselves more easily. The new software is available and documented here [SeaBee-no/SeaBee-Drone2Cloud](#). It is also available as a downloadable .exe file.

Data analysis

Image processing

Once the images have been uploaded to Sigma’s MinIO in the correct folder structure, an automated script on the server detects new missions and initiates processing. This process is fully documented on GitHub under [SeaBee Documentation](#).

In brief, the images are processed using OpenDroneMap to create orthomosaics. After processing, the orthomosaics are published on a public GeoNode server (geonode.seabee.sigma2.no) where they can be accessed and viewed directly from any computer.

Machine Learning Integration

The SeaBee project has developed a machine learning (ML) model trained to detect seabird species on orthomosaics. This model was trained using manual annotations from images stored on MinIO, which provided labeled data to train a custom ResNET (residual network) model capable of detecting species in new orthomosaics uploaded to the platform (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Seabird detections by the machine learning model on an orthomosaic on the public GeoNode server.

The first generation of the model is called “nina_seabirds_rgb_20240130”. This model is trained on 10,720 individuals, from 51 different mosaics. The number of individuals used for each species in the training process is detailed in the Table 1.

Table 1. Overview of all annotated bird species used to train the first generation model (nina_seabirds_rgb_20240130).

Black-headed Gull	4512	Lapwing	9
Lesser Black-backed Gull	1962	Mute Swan	9
Herring Gull	1319	Shag	8
Common/Arctic Tern	837	Bar-headed Goose	7
Great Cormorant	590	Goldpoop	7
Common Gull	396	Great Crested Grebe	7
Greylag Goose	392	Coot	6
Great Black-backed Gull	228	Guillemot	6
Barnacle Goose	195	Sheep	6
Eider	50	Cormorant/Shag	4
Crow	44	Red-breasted Merganser	4
Gull indet.	27	Wigeon	3
Oystercatcher	26	Arctic Tern	2
Mallard	18	Black Guillemot	2
Mask DONT ANALYZE	16	Canada Goose	1
Tufted Duck	13	Duck Indet.	1
Jackdaw	12	Goose indet.	1

Validation

Each night, the automated detections generated by SeaBee’s ML model are transferred to the NINA database. The orthomosaics and detection data are then made accessible on NINA’s internal visualization platforms, utilizing GeoNode’s WMS to display them on [SeaBee - URBPOP](#).

Within URBPOP, several endpoints are available, but the Count module is currently the most widely used for validation purposes. In this module, users can filter detections and perform manual counts by clicking directly on the map interface. This module is secured behind a login wall; however, a few figures of the interface are provided below for reference (Figure 6-8).

Figure 6. Counting interface with automatic detections from the ML model (blue squares). For each manually counted bird, species, activity (e.g. on nest, on land, on water), sex (male/female) and age (e.g. adult, juvenile, pullus) is determined if available.

Figure 7. The automated detections and manual count can be filtered to show only one species, in this case herring gull. The interface shows the number of automated detections (on the bottom on the left), as well as the number of manually counted birds (in the middle on the left).

Figure 8. Manually counted birds (red circles) of lesser black-backed gulls on top of automated detections (blue squares).

Annotation

The annotation module enables the team to pick specific data for further training of the ML model. This module is also behind a login wall and used by a smaller group of users. The Annotation Module uses a different table in the database and works independently from other modules. Only detections from selected layers and manual counts from the Count Module are transferred to the annotation database.

The latest version of the annotation module displays automated detections (blue squares) and where these are validated overlaid by red squares. Users can identify false detections by spotting blue squares, making it easier to visually verify errors (Figure 9).

Figure 9. interface form the validation interface. Red squares are automated detections which have been validated in the counting module. Automated detections which was not validated (e.g. misclassification) are indicated by blue squared. Blue circles indicates birds that where not detected by the ML model.

The module also highlights counts that do not overlap with any detection as blue circles (Figure 9). These circles represent counts that were either done after data was initially transferred to annotations, or more critically, counted individuals missed by the ML model. When individuals are missed by the ML model, users create a new annotation box (square) around each unmarked individual, effectively marking them for future training.

After the annotation step, all annotations are consolidated into a single, standardized structure. A script then applies a series of overarching adjustments to the annotation files before they are sent to ResNET for model retraining. These adjustments include:

- **Translating WMS Links to File Paths:** The script converts WMS links to direct file paths on MinIO, making it easier for the model to access and process the relevant image files during training.
- **Merging Species Categories:** For certain species that are difficult to distinguish in the model detections (e.g., various tern species), the script merges these categories into a single grouping. This streamlines the model training by focusing on the key distinctions between species that the model can reliably identify.

Appendix 1: Equipment list

Each team is issued an equipment package which contains:

- DJI Mavic 3 Case
 - DJI MAVIC 3M/3T/3T,
 - Remote controller
 - Four drone batteries
 - Charging station and cables
 - Two SD card
- Internet link
- Raspberry pi
- GPS unit with extra AA batteries
- External hard drive
- Drysuits and life vests for every person
- PLBs for every person
- Waterproof bags
- Power bank
- First aid kit

Appendix 2: Drone regulations

RULES IN THE OPEN CATEGORY

<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1 Registration at flydrone.no 2 Operator number displayed on the drone 3 Liability insurance 4 Maximum altitude 120 meters 5 Procedures and overview over personnel for operators with more than one pilot 6 Flying within visual line of sight (VLOS) 7 No dropping of objects 8 No transport of dangerous goods 9 16 years minimum age to fly alone 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1:1 rule The horizontal distance from uninvolved persons can be no less than the vertical altitude of the drone above ground. 	Sub-category	Area	Drone	Pilot competency
		A1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Avoid flying over uninvolved persons • No flying over assemblies of people 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • C0-marked by the manufacturer 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User manual
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No flying over uninvolved persons 	<p>No marking:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Below <u>250 gram</u> • Maximum speed 19 m/s 	
		A2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Minimum 30 m horizontal distance from uninvolved persons • Minimum 5 meters from uninvolved persons when using the low speed mode (max 3 m/s) • 1:1 rule 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • C2-marked by the manufacturer 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User manual • A1/A3 course and exam • A2 course • Fly self-training in A1/A3 • A2 exam
		A3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Minimum <u>150 meters</u> from residential, commercial, industrial or recreational areas • No uninvolved persons in the area of operation • Minimum 30 meters from uninvolved persons entering the area. • 1:1 rule 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • C2, C3 or C4-marked by the manufacturer 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User manual • A1/A3 course and exam
				<p>No marking:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Below <u>25 kg</u> • No date limitation 	